

SUMMARY

Introduction

Prostaglandins (PGE₂, PGF₂ α , PGI₂, PGD₂) are vital lipid mediators in reproduction, facilitating cervical ripening and uterine contractions during labor. Understanding their roles is crucial, as labor induction mechanisms remain unclear, hindering prediction of premature birth, a major cause of neonatal morbidity/mortality. While many biomarkers are unreliable, monitoring urinary prostaglandin metabolites offers a non-invasive approach, as their levels increase with labor

The research hypothesis is that prostaglandin levels in the urine may be associated with labour and may be detectable in preterm labour.

Study aims:

1. To determine whether the urinary prostaglandins PGF₂ α and prostaglandin metabolites (PGFM, PGEM, PGIM, t-PGDM) and 8-isoprostane concentrations change with labour and/or cervical changes, at term and preterm and are associated with timing of delivery in those with threatening preterm labour (TPTL).
2. To perform a discovery analysis on a subset of samples using a mass-spectrometry-based eicosanoid panel and determine if any additional eicosanoids are associated with labour.

Methods

Participants and sample collection: This research was conducted after obtaining the appropriate consent from the bioethics committee (REB18-0648, May 7, 2018). All participants provided written consent for collection of urine and medical record data on mode of delivery and pregnancy outcomes. The recruitment took place in Foothills Medical Centre (Calgary, Alberta) between May 2018 and July 2020. Participants were classified based on gestational age (term: 37-42 weeks or preterm: <37 weeks) and presence or absence of labour. Finally, five key groups were identified: term non-labour (TNL), n=32; term labour (TL), n=49; preterm non-labour controls (PTNL), n=15; threatened preterm labour with preterm delivery (TPTL-PTD), n=43; or threatened preterm labour with term delivery (TPTL-TD), n=44. Term non-labour participants were recruited at presentation for induction or caesarean section after 37 weeks gestation with no symptoms of labour. Term labour was defined as spontaneous delivery between 37-42 weeks gestation. Preterm non-labour controls were recruited either at presentation for non-delivery related reasons (n=12/15) or at presentation for induction or caesarean section at <37 weeks with no symptoms of labour (n=3/15). Threatened preterm labour (<37 weeks) was diagnosed clinically, with preterm births excluded for medical reasons, eg. abnormal fetal heart rate, uterine problems and maternal conditions.

Urine samples were collected at recruitment and frozen at -80°C prior to analysis. Clinical data were also collected, including cervical dilation, based on which a cervical score (analogous to the Bishop scale) was calculated to assess cervical ripening and proximity to spontaneous delivery (a cervical score of -10: fully dilated and a cervical score of 4: long and closed cervix).

Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA): The study measured the concentrations of several compounds related to prostaglandin metabolism in urine using ELISA kits (Cayman Chemical). All samples were measured randomly and each sample was analyzed in duplicate. Sample dilutions were different depending on the compound being measured.

Urinary concentration correction: Urinary prostaglandin metabolite concentrations were corrected for urine specific gravity (SG – specific gravity) using the Boeniger method.

Statistical analyses confirmed that creatinine was too weakly correlated with specific gravity, therefore its measurement was not used for normalization.

Reverse phase ultra high-performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry: A subset of 24 urine samples were selected for a discovery analysis using a mass-spectrometry-based eicosanoid panel. Eicosanoids were isolated from urine by solid phase extraction. The samples were then analyzed using a triple quadrupole linear ion trap mass spectrometer (Sciex 6500 Qtrap). Eicosanoids were quantitated by comparison with reference standards and the data analysis was performed using Analyst and MultiQuant software.

Statistics and data presentation: Normality was checked with Shapiro-Wilk. Prostaglandin levels were adjusted for urinary concentration and log-transformed. Group differences were tested via t-test. Cervical ripening association used combined groups and Spearman's correlation. Linear regression assessed association with days from collection to delivery. Data are presented as mean or median. Significance set at $p < 0.05$. Analysis used R and GraphPad Prism 9 software. Discovery cohort eicosanoid data analysis was omitted due to small size and low detection rates.

Results

Participant demographics: Table 1 presents the demographic and clinical data of the participants. Compared to the TNL group, women in the TL group had a higher gestational age both at the time of sperm collection (39.7 vs. 38.6 weeks, $p < 0.001$) and at delivery (39.7 vs. 38.6 weeks, $p < 0.001$). Mothers in the PTNL, TPTL-PTD, and TPTL-TD groups were significantly younger than those in the TNL group (mean approx. 31–31.7 years vs. 34.5 years).

Urinary prostaglandin levels with labour and gestation: The TL group had significantly higher concentrations of PGFM, PGEM, and PGF2 α than the TNL group (Table 2, Fig. 2). Among participants with preterm birth, PGIM levels were higher in the TPTL-TD group than in the TPTL-PTD group, while other prostaglandins did not differ between these groups. No correlation between prostaglandin levels and gestational age was found (Fig. 2).

Since four participants in the TPTL-PTD group had PPRM, an additional analysis was performed after their exclusion. The only difference observed earlier—in PGIM levels—became statistically insignificant ($p = 0.071$ instead of $p = 0.036$).

Urinary prostaglandin levels and cervical ripening: In full-term pregnancies, a positive correlation was found between PGEM levels and cervical ripening ($R^2 = 0.069$; $p = 0.033$), while other prostaglandins did not show any significant correlations. In preterm infants, t-PGDM and PGIM levels were negatively correlated with cervical ripening (t-PGDM: $R^2 = 0.081$; $p = 0.017$; PGIM: $R^2 = 0.070$; $p = 0.035$). Other prostaglandins (PGFM, PGEM, 8-isoprostane, PGF2 α) showed no correlation.

Prostaglandin levels and time to delivery: In a linear regression analysis of participants at risk of preterm birth, higher levels of PGFM, 8-isoprostane, and PGF2 α were significantly associated with a shorter time to delivery. In contrast, higher levels of PGIM were associated with a longer time to delivery. All of these associations were statistically significant.

Discovery cohort eicosanoid profile: In order to identify additional eicosanoids in the urine of pregnant women, 24 samples were analyzed in a discovery panel based on mass spectrometry, 6 from each group: TPTL-PTD, PTNL, TL, and TNL (Table 3). Of the 147 eicosanoids measured, 66 were not detected. A total of 81 compounds were detected in at least one sample, with concentrations ranging from 0.01 to 1016.17 pmol/ml. Four eicosanoids were detected in all samples (9,10-diHOME, 9,10-EpOME, 9-HODE, 13-HODE), and 20 were detected in $\geq 50\%$ of samples (Table 4). This group included representatives of prostaglandins, HETE, EET, DiHOME, diHETrE, isoprostanes, and nitrofatty acids, among others.

Discussion: The study showed that the metabolites of prostaglandins PGFM and PGEM are elevated in the urine of women giving birth at term, but their levels do not increase before the onset of labor, which excludes their usefulness as biomarkers for predicting labor. In threatened preterm labor, only PGIM showed a slight difference between women who delivered prematurely and those who

ultimately delivered at term. PGEM levels correlated with cervical ripening in full-term pregnancies, confirming the role of PGE₂ in this process, although it is unclear whether this is a cause or effect of cervical ripening. Unlike previous studies of amniotic fluid, no differences in PGE₂ and PGF₂ α metabolite levels were detected in urine between women with preterm birth and those who delivered at term. The exception was PGIM, which was found to be higher in women at risk of preterm birth who ultimately delivered at term.

PGIM, a metabolite of the relaxant PGI₂, could theoretically influence the onset of labor, but in the study, its levels did not change before delivery, and its contribution to explaining the variability in time to delivery was small ($R^2 = 0.062$), ruling out its usefulness as a biomarker for preterm labor. In addition to prostaglandins, many other eicosanoids were detected in the urine of pregnant women, including HETE (LOX), EET, and diHOME (CYP450), often in concentrations comparable to or higher than prostaglandins. Some of them (5-HETE, 12,13-diHOME, 9,10-diHOME) may be associated with an increased risk of spontaneous preterm birth and show better predictive potential than prostaglandins, although their significance may depend on BMI. Further research on these molecules may help identify more reliable biomarkers for preterm birth. A limitation of the study is the combination of women with preterm birth and PPRM into a single group of threatened preterm birth, even though the molecular mechanisms of these events may differ. In the future, it is recommended that these groups be analyzed separately with a larger number of participants.

Conclusion: The study confirms that although prostaglandins and their metabolites change during labor, none of the analyzed compounds increase before labor begins, which excludes their usefulness as biomarkers for predicting both full-term and preterm labor. At the same time, a number of other eicosanoids present in at least half of the samples have been identified that may play a hitherto underestimated role in pregnancy and labor. The authors emphasize the need for further research on these non-prostaglandin eicosanoids using lipidomic methods to assess their biological and clinical potential.

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